

The NOIRLab/CHARA Connection Marks Decadal Milestones Up to 40 Years

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Just one decade ago, the Georgia State University (GSU) Center for High Angular Resolution Astronomy (CHARA) first offered open access to the CHARA Array, making time available through the NOAO Telescope Allocation Committee (TAC) twice per year (Figure 1). GSU absorbed the associated costs, thus taking leadership in developing the science community of interferometer users. Starting at about 10 nights per year, that allocation has increased. Thanks to NSF grant support through the Mid-Scale Innovations Program (MSIP), CHARA now offers up to 100 nights per year through open competition.

The 10-year mark on open access recalls other milestones. The Array was dedicated two decades ago. At that time, its 300-meter telescope baselines provided the highest optical resolution available to astronomers. After 20 years, with the same telescopes and baselines, this is still true.

The CHARA and National Observatory links go back even further. Approximately 40 years ago, Harold McAlister, while working as a postdoc for Kitt Peak astronomer Roger Lynds, matured speckle interferometry as a methodology. Hal departed Tucson with the immediate goal of pursuing speckle methods and with the germ of an idea for an optical array. In the succeeding years he formed CHARA as a major GSU initiative. While conducting and fostering modern binary star research, he prepared the ground for the CHARA Array, motivating, promoting, and shepherding the program to

Figure 2: The E2 telescope and the start of the 150-meter vacuum pipe that conducts the light beam to the combining area. Credit: S. Golden/Georgia State University

Figure 1: The Mt. Wilson 100" Hooker dome, surrounded by the CHARA Array. Key to Array elements: at 2:30, the E1 and E2 domes; at 3:00, the central laboratory and the offices; at 7:00, light pipes to the S1 and S2 telescopes; at 9:00, the W1 dome. Credit: Georgia State University

success. NOAO engaged substantially in the Array design and construction. In addition to scientific and technical staff participation, NOAO was the second-largest Array contractor, mainly for design, fabrication, and implementation of specialized array elements.

Now 22 years after the Array dedication, succeeding development of beam combiners and detectors extend the Array performance in sensitivity, spectral coverage, and imaging power (Figures 2–3). Major recent or in-progress developments include higher-performance visible and infrared beam combiners and adaptive optics on all telescopes. Programs in preparation include addition of a movable telescope with an optical fiber link to the fixed array and continuing design work on possible future Array upgrades to larger apertures.

Open access is now an essential feature of the CHARA Array operation. Records show that during the decade, the NOAO/NOIRLab TACs have processed 303 proposals representing over 350 distinct participating observers (PI + CoI). Community proposals span a broad range of science goals (see sidebar).

A sample of community science programs conducted with the CHARA Array

One main focus is measuring the angular diameters of stars across the H-R diagram, from low- to high-mass stars along the main sequence and for stars at different evolutionary stages. Tyler Ellis [1] recently used the CHARA Array to measure the radius of the exoplanet host star HD 97658. These results were used to refine the physical properties of the transiting super-Earth HD 97658 b. In a similar analysis, José Caballero [2] measured the radius of the host star Gl 486 to help derive the properties of the rocky transiting exoplanet Gl 486 b.

Matthew De Furio [3] conducted a multiplicity survey of 26 intermediate mass A-type stars within 80 pc and found a companion frequency of 0.19 at separations between 0.29 and 5.48 au. At the higher masses, Cyprien Lanthermann [4] surveyed 29 O-stars to search for companions at angular separations between 0.5 to 50 mas and found a higher companion frequency of 0.66 ± 0.13 .

Noel Richardson [5] measured the first dynamical mass of a nitrogen-rich Wolf-Rayet star by mapping the visual orbit of WR 133 with the CHARA Array and combining his data with radial velocity measurements. The results suggest that WR 133 might have formed through binary interactions. Leslie Morales and Eric Sandquist [6] mapped the orbit of the brightest member of the Praesepe cluster, ϵ Cnc, to determine precise dynamical masses. Comparison with evolutionary tracks yielded an age of 637 ± 19 Myr. Willie Torres [7] spatially resolved the orbits of the close, faint companions to Castor A and B for the first time. Combined with historical observations spanning the past three centuries, he measured the three-dimensional orbits of the four stars in Castor A and B and determined the stellar masses with a precision better than 1%. The interferometric radii of the primary stars in each subsystem were used to infer an age of 290 Myr.

Makoto Kishimoto [8] resolved the inner dusty region around the supermassive black hole at the center of the active galaxy NGC 4151. The results show an elongation perpendicular to the emerging jet, consistent with emission from an equatorial dusty ring. A flaring disk geometry could explain differences in the inner region probed by the near-infrared wavelengths and the outer region studied by high-angular-resolution observations in the mid-infrared.

Elias Aydi and Laura Chomiuk [9] obtained target-of-opportunity observations of five bright novae outbursts to monitor the angular expansion of the ejecta and the development of asymmetries over time.

A major development of recent years is the capability to record resolved stellar images, giving greater insight into the physics of surface activity. Rachael Roettenbacher [10] (Figure 4) studied the rapidly rotating, magnetically active giant Zeta And, with time evolution confirming a persistent polar spot and variable lower latitude spots. Ryan Norris [11] followed convective structures on the supergiant AZ Cyg, finding large structures observed for five years and a smaller structure that was more transient.

Figure 3: **Left:** Infrared image of AZ Cyg *Credit: Norris et al. 2021*. **Right:** Temperature map of zeta Andromeda over range 3600–4600K. *Credit: Roettenbacher et al. 2016*

The next generation of instrumentation at the CHARA Array offers improved sensitivity and options for combining all six telescopes across multiple wavelength regions. The MIRC-X

and MYSTIC instruments operate simultaneously and combine the light from all six telescopes in the near infrared H and K bands. They provide sensitivity down to H=7.5 mag

Figure 4: Beam synthesis facility. Optical delay room. The variable delay lines extend toward the upper left. Metrology, beam compression, switching, and dispersion compensation are on the tables in the foreground. *Credit: S. Golden/Georgia State University*

and a range of spectral resolutions from $R=50$ to $R=1700$. The MIRC-X and MYSTIC beam combiners were built and commissioned by teams at the University of Michigan and Exeter University, led by John Monnier and Stefan Kraus. The main science drivers include imaging stellar surfaces and circumstellar disks around young stars to better understand planet formation.

A new visible light, 6-telescope combiner called Stellar Parameters and Images with a Cophased Array (SPICA) has been installed at the CHARA Array by a team from the Observatoire de la Côte d'Azur led by Denis Mourard. The instrument features low ($R=150$), medium ($R=4300$), and high ($R=13,200$) spectral resolution modes. One of the main science goals of SPICA is to conduct a survey of 1,000 stars to provide a large and homogeneous set of angular diameter measurements and stellar parameters across the HR-diagram. The higher spectral resolution modes will be available for spectral imaging of stellar surfaces and environments and kinematic studies of brighter stars. Time on SPICA is expected to be offered to the community starting in 2024.

Development work is underway on a new, near-infrared, 3-beam combiner called SILMARIL that seeks to extend the

sensitivity of the Array down to 10–11 mag in the H and K bands. The SILMARIL project is led by Theo ten Brummelaar of GSU. The improved sensitivity will help astronomers resolve the inner cores of a larger sample of active galaxies.

Open-access time at the CHARA Array is available through the [NOIRLab time allocation system](#). CHARA staff provides assistance to new observers to help with developing science programs, planning observations, collecting data, and providing reduced and calibrated data files. Guest observers are encouraged to participate in the observations, and travel support is available for those who wish to visit the Array. CHARA also offers the option to participate in observations remotely through a VNC connection to a virtual machine that runs the control software.

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